

Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education in Civics Subjects Based on *Project Citizen* at SMAN 6 Tangerang Regency, Banten

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe the implementation of anti-corruption education in Pancasila and Citizenship Education subjects through citizen project-based activities or learning. This research is a qualitative descriptive study conducted at SMAN 6 Tangerang Banten Regency in class 10 Social Studies. Sources of data in this study consisted of principals, vice principals in the field of curriculum, PPKn subject teachers and students. Technical analysis of the data in this study was conducted in three phases, with the way: classifying, reducing, and eliminating data that are not in accordance with the research objectives, then presented descriptively. As a result, the implementation of anti-corruption education is carried out through an assessment of problems related to corruption with a presentation panel consisting of 4 parts, namely the problem section, policy alternatives, the proposed settlement section, and the action plan section. Through these activities, students are expected to acquire the desired attitude such as honesty, caring, self-reliance, discipline, responsibility, hard work, humility, courage and justice.

KEYWORDS: anti-corruption education, Pancasila and citizenship education, project citizen.

PRELIMINARY

Corruption is a crucial problem that occurs in Indonesia. Corruption is growing very rapidly and is widespread in various aspects of people's lives. Of course, effective efforts are needed to solve corruption in Indonesia. Efforts to introduce anti-corruption culture must be carried out early. One of them is through education, both elementary and high school. Anti-corruption education efforts will certainly be an effective solution in minimizing corruption. The Indonesian government started its efforts in 2009 through the Ministry of National Education seeking teaching materials in the form of anti-corruption education modules in elementary to high school. However, these efforts are certainly not a guarantee in developing the content of anti-corruption education materials in these schools.

The form of efforts to combat corruption is certainly a very interesting study in today's world. The problem of corruption is certainly the first discussion around the world. Every time, every hour, of course, the community is always in contact with the government bureaucracy, which in general is very vulnerable to corruption. It is also possible that every human interaction, whether in the family, school, community, even on social media, of course there will be elements of a criminal act of corruption. Therefore, it is necessary to have a strategy and maximum effort by the government to minimize it. The government views educational institutions as being one of the effective institutions in introducing forms and culture of corruption to students from an early age, namely through Anti-Corruption Education. With anti-corruption knowledge from an early age, it is expected to be able to produce future leaders of the nation with an anti-corruption spirit in Indonesia. Therefore, a strategic and systematic effort is needed in teaching anti-corruption education materials to students so that students with character will be formed based on anti-corruption values. Thus the basic values in the formation of laws and regulations, especially anti-corruption education, must use Pancasila as a philosophical foundation, namely as a view of life, awareness and legal ideals so that constitutional standardization will be achieved based on the basic state values of Pancasila as a pure education system (Sutrisno, 2016).

Education cannot be separated from the process of human life. Through education, humans know how they can live and interact socially. Therefore, as long as there is life, as long as humans will always exist in the world. One form of solving human problems is education. Education today is certainly the key to various problems experienced by the Indonesian nation today. When humans are able to understand the real dimensions of education, they will be able to take advantage of every moment in their lives. Various problems that occur in Indonesia today certainly require a quick and concrete solution. Of course this can be done through education. The problem of corruption is certainly an interesting object of study to be studied in general.

Anti-corruption education is one of the efforts made by the government in instilling an anti-corruption attitude in students in the school environment. Corruption itself is not an act that harms many people by taking advantage of position for personal

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gain. Corruption is carried out in ways that are not in accordance with regulations, such as: bribery, extortion and fraud have the potential to occur in the government sector which will become a disease that destroys all aspects of life (Hamilton-Hart, 2001). Basically, anti-corruption education can be interpreted as an educational program that explains and overcomes various corruptions that occur in the community by planting an anti-corruption spirit as early as possible with the aim of building and increasing citizen awareness of the dangers and consequences of corruption. Anti-corruption education has three objectives, *first*, to form knowledge and understanding of forms of corruption and its aspects. *Second*, changing perceptions and attitudes towards corruption. *Third*, forming new skills and abilities aimed at fighting corruption (Hakim, 2010).

In comparison, the development of anti-corruption education in Lithuania has been carried out systematically since 2015 by providing students with an understanding to be able to distinguish between corruption crimes and other crimes, providing logical and rational arguments why corruption is considered a crime, and showing ways that can be done. Taken to reduce the incidence of corruption. There are several things that need to be developed in the anti-corruption education process in the classroom, namely knowledge about corruption, developing anti-corruption attitudes, changing anti-corruption attitudes, moral education, and developing anti-corruption characters (*Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Lithuania*, 2006, p. 22).

In addition to this, of course, it is also necessary to instill an anti-corruption attitude in students in every learning process. Attitude is an important component in developing the culture or character of students in doing good. According to Sax (1997, p. 493) attitude is "*a preference along a dimension of favorableness to unfavorableness to a particular group, institution, concept, or object.*"

The government must guarantee and oversee anti-corruption education so that the initial goals and targets in the implementation of anti-corruption education can really be understood and digested properly by teachers who support subjects related to anti-corruption education. Not only teachers but the role of school institutions in the implementation and management of the education system must also take part. Without work equally good between the teacher and the headmaster of the school institution as policy makers directly, it is impossible educational programs of government anti-corruption discourse since the year 2009 until now can be achieved.

The subject of Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn) is a compulsory subject in the 2013 curriculum. This subject certainly contains material related to anti-corruption education. Bearing in mind that anti-corruption education materials do not stand alone as mandatory subjects. Similarly, character education that although it has not become the eyes of subjects themselves that are taught in the learning process at school, but the matter of anti-corruption education and character education materials should be integrated with materials other subjects, especially on subjects Education Religion and PPKn. In line with this, of course, Civics subjects are suitable as a medium for the transformation of knowledge in Anti-Corruption Education in every classroom learning.

Civics is a subject that contains the values of national character. Civics is an education that functions to build awareness of citizens in carrying out their rights and obligations as citizens in an effort to form an identity for citizens of a nation. Civics learning must rely on basic citizenship skills (*civic competence*) for all levels. For this reason, so that learning is effective and able to equip students with knowledge and achieve basic citizenship skills, in developing learning activities it is necessary to pay attention to several things. *First*, Civics Learning Activities are structured to provide assistance to educators (teachers), in order to carry out the learning process professionally. *Second*, Civics learning activities contain a series of activities that must be carried out by students in sequence to achieve basic competencies. *Third*, determining the sequence of Civics learning activities must be in accordance with the hierarchy of learning material concepts. *Fourth*, the formulation of statements in Civics learning activities contains at least two elements that reflect the management of students' learning experiences.

Civics has an important role in efforts to foster the character of the younger generation who think critically about global issues to be able to explore, develop and express their own values and opinions. This is of course the same as what was stated (Zahabioun, Yousefy, Yarmohammadian, & Keshtiaray, 2013) regarding Global Citizenship Education that:

Education for Global Citizenship gives children and young people the opportunity to develop critical thinking about complex global issues in the safe space of the classroom, encouraging children and young people to explore, develop and express their own values and opinions, whilst listening to and respecting other people's points of view, to care about the planet and to develop empathy with, and an active concern for, those with whom they share it.

Of course this shows that education must really be able to develop the characteristics of citizens based on the character of a country. To grow the characteristics of citizens in the Civics learning process, of course, innovation is needed. PPKn learning innovations can be done by applying learning approaches Civics from the content-oriented approach (*content-based curriculum*) to a direction that is more emphasis on the process (*process based curriculum*). This idea is intended so that through PPKn, citizens can be formed who are more independent in understanding and finding solutions to the problems they face and are able to make decisions that are best for themselves, their environment and society. These abilities have been summarized into three Civics learning objectives which are also known as the orientation of Civics learning objectives for the formation of democratic citizens, namely to

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form *good and smart citizens*, *participative citizens*, and *responsible citizens*. Wahab & Sapriya (2011, pp. 327–328). Thus, it is hoped that through an innovative, effective and efficient learning process with various approaches used, it is able to implement anti-corruption education in Civics subjects well.

Civics subjects have a very noble mission. In relation to the mission of Civics, Maftuh (2008, p. 137) argues that with the demands of the development of society and the life of a state that is so advanced with all its challenges, Citizenship Education today has the following missions: 1) Civics as Political Education; 2) Civics as Value Education; 3) Civics as Nationalism Education; 4) Civics as Legal Education; 5) Civics as Multicultural Education; and 6) Civics as a Conflict Resolution Education.

The mission is certainly one of the goals of how Civics subjects can be a benchmark in the implementation of anti-corruption values in students as one of the values education that needs to be developed. As a form of implementation of anti-corruption education in the subjects PPKn as any one of educational value. So it must be implemented optimally in every learning process. The 2013 curriculum explains that the learning process efforts that are developed in each learning process must be oriented to the application of national character values based on the basic values of the Pancasila state. The development of social aspects, knowledge and skills must be a top priority with the hope that the learning objectives conveyed can actually be achieved.

The *scientific* learning approach in the 2013 Curriculum is certainly an effective effort in developing aspects of the knowledge and skills of students. *Scientific* learning is a teaching learner that adopts the steps of scientists in building knowledge through the scientific method. Learning *scientific* is not simply acquiring the capability aspects of knowledge, skills and attitudes will but tend to how knowledge skills and attitudes acquired directly by the learners in each of the learning process. One of the *scientific* learning models that can be applied in Civics learning with Anti-Corruption Education material is the *project citizen* learning model.

Learning *project citizen* is learning that developed in California in 1992 and then developed into the program nationwide by the *Center for Civic Education (CCE)* and the National Conference of Law-making body in the year 1995. The model learning *project citizen* is a learning model based on the problem to develop knowledge, skills and civic character that encourage the level of citizen participation in the government system. The teacher's role in this learning model is as an instructor and facilitator who provides students with new sources of information, helps establish direct contacts and equips students to be active and critical.

The *project citizen* learning model focuses on the involvement of students in the overall learning process in terms of attitudes, knowledge and skills. Based on the *CCE* document, the *project citizen* learning process is developed in a scenario and learning guidelines that include the following six steps:

1. Identifying public policy problems that exist in society; In this step, the class is facilitated to be able to identify various problems that exist in the community through observations, interviews, and documentation studies conducted in groups.
2. Choose the problem as the focus of the class study. In this step, the class is facilitated to examine the various problems and then choose the one that is most feasible to solve.
3. Collecting information related to problems that are the focus of class studies; In this step the class is facilitated to collect the information needed in order to solve the problem from various relevant and available information sources, such as libraries, mass media, professionals and experts, government officials, non-governmental organizations, and community leaders and members.
4. Develop a class portfolio. In this step, the class develops a portfolio in the form of a collection of group work results in solving the problem and presents it as a whole in the form of an exhibition panel that can be viewed together, which describes the interrelationship of problems, policy alternatives, support for policy alternatives, and action plans to implement the policy that.
5. Presenting class portfolios in a simulated hearing; and In this step, the entire portfolio that has been developed is then presented and exhibited to the school community and the community.
6. Conduct a depositional study on the learning experience carried out. In the last step, return to the classroom to reflect or settle and reflect on the learning outcomes achieved through all these activities (Winataputra & Budimansyah, 2007, pp. 1–2).

The *project citizen* learning model is certainly very effective when applied to Civics subjects. This is certainly related to the aspect of citizenship skills developed in Civics learning materials. Through this *project citizen* learning model, students try to form their identity independently and build community relations (Budimansyah, 2008, p. 183). The *project citizen* learning model in Civics Education learning on the Materials of the National Legal and Judicial System in Indonesia is expected to have an effect on inculcating the values of anti-corruption attitudes well for high school students in understanding corruption.

This agrees with Cogan & Derricott (1998) that there are three important components in Civics Subjects, namely *civic knowledge* which is related to citizen knowledge, *civic skill* is related to the intellectual and participatory skills of relevant citizens, *civic disposition* is a civic character that implies character. public or private which is essential for the maintenance and

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development of constitutional democracy. One of the characteristics and competencies of citizenship that is expected according to the explanation above is to instill anti-corruption values from an early age.

Based on the background of the problem as described above, the core issue and at the same time the focus of the study in this research is how to implement anti-corruption education in *project citizen*-based Civics. Considering that the formulation of the problem above is so broad, the researcher specifically wants to reveal several problems as follows: (1) How is the implementation of anti-corruption education materials in Civics subjects? (2) How is the implementation of anti-corruption education in *project citizen*-based Civics subjects? Thus, the purpose of this research is first, to find out how to include anti-corruption education material content in Civics subjects. Second, to find out how to apply the *project citizen* learning model to anti-corruption education materials that have been included in the content of Civics.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a qualitative descriptive study. This research was conducted at SMAN 6 Tangerang Regency, Banten Province, in class 10 Social Studies. Sources of data in this study consisted of principals, deputy head of the school curriculum areas, teacher's eyes lessons PPKn and learners. Data collection techniques in this study are through observation, interviews and documentation. The data analysis technique in this study was carried out in three stages by classifying, reducing and eliminating data that were not in accordance with the research objectives, then described descriptively. The next stage is the process of making conclusions in accordance with the research objectives.

RESEARCH RESULT

The PPKn learning process certainly needs to be carried out continuously and systematically. A systematic and measurable learning pattern will develop scientific competence in students. The process of transforming scientific values in students is certainly a benchmark for achieving the learning objectives to be achieved. The implementation of anti-corruption education in Civics subjects using the *project citizen* learning model can be done through several stages.

Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education Materials in Civics Subjects. The process of implementing anti-corruption education materials must make several elements of the implementation process this can be done through several stages of implementation, namely the development of the Civics Learning Curriculum.

The content of the material developed in the Civics learning process consists of the national legal and judicial system which is taught in the Civics Class 10 Social Sciences material. Through this material, material about the definition of corruption can be inserted with the aim that students are able to understand the meaning of the word and the definition of corruption correctly and correctly, students are able to explain the history of corruption and eradication of corruption in Indonesia correctly and students are able to explain the forms of corruption. .

While the next material that needs to be conveyed to students consists of material related to efforts and the role of eradicating corruption with the aim of learning so that students are able to explain various efforts to eradicate corruption, students are able to explain their role in efforts to eradicate corruption in the daily lives of students. Students are able to understand anti-corruption values

Through anti-corruption education learning, students will contribute more in developing anti-corruption values or attitudes in students. The content of anti-corruption education learning materials in PPKn learning is carried out through several things, one of which is preparing learning tools, preparing learning materials consisting of first, understanding corruption crimes up to the second, efforts and participation in eradicating corruption.

These two materials were delivered at the first meeting with a duration of 2 x 45 minutes. This is intended so that students can absorb various problems and a basic understanding of corruption in general, so that in the second meeting, students will be presented with various problems about corruption to be solved through the *project citizen* learning model. With the hope that participants are able to implement knowledge and knowledge in anti-corruption education materials into solutions to the problems of corruption that occur.

DISCUSSION

Responding to the problem of corruption that is increasingly prevalent in society, especially among the government elite. An anti-corruption action is needed. Anti-corruption is a policy to prevent and eliminate opportunities for corruption to develop. Prevention in question is how to increase individual awareness not to commit corruption and how to save money and state assets. Opportunities for the development of corruption can be eliminated by improving the system, namely; legal system and institutional system. And the existence of moral improvement and well-being for the community, moral improvement can be given one premises n PPKn their subjects in schools and their socialization-disseminate the values and principles of anti-

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corruption. Besides, the government also participated in the efforts and build the institutions that integrity in mendoreong p emberantas an act of criminal corruption.

In relation to human improvement, anti-corruption measures include: (Rifai, 2018) 1. Improving human morals as believers, namely by optimizing the role of religion in eradicating corruption. This means that religious leaders try to strengthen the emotional bond between religion and its people, state firmly that corruption is a disgraceful act, invite people to distance themselves from all forms of corrupt behavior, and foster community courage to fight corruption; 2. Improving the nation's morale, namely diverting family, clan, ethnic and ethnic loyalties to national loyalty; 3. Increasing individual and community legal awareness through anti-corruption socialization and education; 4. Eradicating poverty through increasing welfare; 5. Choose leaders (all levels) who are clean, honest, anti-corruption, caring, responsive (responsive) and can be role models for those they lead. Anti-corruption efforts in various countries often fail.

The values of anti - corruption efforts to fight or eradicate corruption are not enough to catch and send corruptors to prison, because the opportunities for corruption are wide open in front of potential corruptors, moreover, there are many arenas for new corruptors to vent their corruption desires. That is why it is necessary to instill anti-corruption values as a prevention effort for the younger generation. Values against corruption needs to be seeded to the younger generation, especially those who are still in kindergarten, elementary, junior high, high school, da n Universities, among others u ntuk prevent and avoid themselves from acts of corruption needed values har us obeyed for anti- corruption measures . These values include ("Religion-Based Anti-Corruption Education," 2016):

1. *Honesty* . Honesty is a basic value that is the main basis for upholding one's integrity. Without honesty, it is impossible for a person to become a person of integrity. A person is required to be able to tell the truth and not lie to himself and others. Honesty will also be carried over in work so that it can fortify oneself against the temptation to cheat.
2. *Concern* . Social care for others makes a person have a loving nature. Individuals with a social spirit will not be tempted to enrich themselves in an unrighteous way but instead try to set aside some of their income to help others.
3. *Independence* . Independence forms a strong character in a person being not too dependent on others. A person who already has an independent personality will not establish relationships with irresponsible parties to achieve temporary benefits .
4. *Discipline* . Discipline is the key to everyone's success. A person who has a strong grip on the value of discipline will not fall into laziness that yearns for wealth in an easy way .
5. *Responsibility* . Responsibility is a very important value in this anti-corruption act. With the value of this responsibility, someone will understand and know what should be done and what the consequences are if they violate it. All forms of activities carried out will be fully accountable to God Almighty, society, state and nation. With this kind of awareness one will not slip into despicable actions.
6. *Hard Work* . Someone who has a passion who will always try to improve the quality of his work for the realization of the greatest public benefit. With hard work a person will get results in accordance with the results. If someone does not have the spirit of hard work, of course that person will take shortcuts to get results quickly (in this case, such as acts of corruption).
7. *Courage* . A person who has a strong character will have the courage to speak the truth and reject all despicable behavior. This person dares to stand alone in the truth even though everyone else is doing deviant acts.
8. *Justice* . A person with good character will realize that what he receives is in accordance with his efforts. Someone who has the value of justice will not demand to get more than what he has tried.

Basically, the process of implementing anti- corruption educational materials in Civics subjects has been developed in general in every lesson carried out. This is considering that one of the efforts that need to be made by school institutions, especially PPKn subject teachers, is how the basic concept values in anti-corruption material can be developed in several ways, both the development of the Civics learning curriculum which contains anti-corruption education materials and the learning process carried out by teachers. So that each component in learning can be integrated as a whole in the learning device. The ultimate goal of this learning process is to prepare the young generation with a global spirit, namely global citizens who will think broadly in overcoming corruption. Global citizenship will foster the character of the younger generation who think critically about global issues to be able to explore, develop and express their own values and opinions (Zahabioun, Yousefy, Yarmohammadian, & Keshtiaray, 2013, p. 199).

Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education in Civics subjects based on *Project Citizen* is a problem-based learning model to develop knowledge, skills and civic character that encourages the level of citizen participation in the government system.

There are several stages in the learning process using *project citizens* after students understand the material at the second meeting, students are directed to be divided into small groups, consisting of 4 students. Each small group is given the task of finding information about the problems that are around them. Then students identify problems in everyday life through discussion in class, asking/interviewing parents/family, reading newspapers both print and online, listening to news and watching TV, looking for

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sources of information via the internet. In this case the research takes the example of the big theme of the lack of transparency of school fees which is taken democratically from the most important problems to be solved.

After that, the students were divided into five groups. Four groups for the large panel and one group for the documentation section. The five groups can be explained as follows. Group 1 is tasked with explaining the problems to be discussed, group 2 evaluating alternative policies, group 3 developing solutions as class policies, group 4 developing action plans. Group 5 is in charge of the documentation section. Each group consists of 5 students. After collecting data from each group, students then arrange portfolio panels and documents. Then it is presented in general in the class according to the study of each group's assignments.

Through *project citizen* learning in Civics lessons, students will develop the nature and values of anti-corruption attitudes. One of the values that can be developed in the anti-corruption education learning process in Civics subjects is honesty, caring, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, courage and justice. These values can be felt directly when students follow each learning process that takes place. Through this learning process, students are more creative and innovate in developing any content of anti-corruption education material which will then become the basis for acting in everyday life, both in the school, family, and community environment.

The implementation of anti-corruption education in Civics learning will certainly result in the attitudes and personalities of students who are progressive in order to solve any problems regarding various corruptions that occur in Indonesia. With the anti-corruption education taught at the high school level, especially grade 10 Social Studies, it will be the basis of anti-corruption science in the future that will highlight anti-corruption attitudes. This implementation will be a reference for teachers to develop anti-corruption education in Civics learning in high school which is based on two concepts, namely the *project citizen* -based learning process with steps that have been systematically developed and the final achievement of learning, namely the achievement of an understanding of values and anti-corruption attitude.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the research developed by the researcher, the conclusions are as follows.

1. The implementation of anti-corruption education materials in Civics subjects is usually carried out in several stages:
 - 1) Mengembangkan learning curriculum PPKn it can be inserted through the material national legal and judicial systems. In this chapter, anti-corruption education will be inserted, namely material on the definition of criminal acts of corruption and material on efforts and the role of eradicating corruption.
 - 2) The learning process Anti-corruption education in Civics subjects can be done by preparing learning tools which consist of media, project citizen models and other reference materials, either field study internet or other study sources. In the learning process, there were two meetings for the first meeting to discuss the basic material of anti-corruption education, while the second meeting had practice learning using *project citizens*.
2. The implementation of anti-corruption education in Civics subjects based on *project citizens* will be the basis of knowledge that can create a generation that has a high and critical anti - corruption attitude in dealing with various corruption cases. The application can be done in several ways: 1) The application of the learning process using the *project citizen* model, students are directed to examine various problems regarding corruption. From each problem is taken the most important to be solved immediately. After finding the main problem , a large group was formed consisting of four components, group 1 – explaining the problem to be discussed, group 2 – evaluating alternative policies, group 3 – developing solutions as class policies, group 4 – developing action plans or actions. Through this process, solutions to the problems discussed will emerge and will serve as a reference for resolution in the form of a *project citizen* presentation panel. 2) The basic values of anti-corruption education will be understood directly by students when through the learning process with the *project citizen* model while the values that will be achieved by students consist of the values of honesty, care, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, courage and justice.

Suggestion

The suggestions that can be conveyed from the conclusions of the study are as follows:

1. Teachers can implement anti-corruption education materials in Civics subjects through several stages as mentioned above.
2. The implementation of anti-corruption education in *project citizen* -based Civics will be the basis of knowledge that can create a generation that has high anti - corruption attitudes, integrity and criticality, by collaborating with varied learning methods according to the subject being studied.

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